

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of hexoses by bromamine-T in alkaline medium

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Manuscript received 17 November 1999, revised 29 September 2000, accepted 8 December 2000

The kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of D-glucose and D-mannose with bromamine-T in alkaline medium have been studied and the rate = $k[\text{BAT}][\text{sugar}][\text{OH}^-]^2$, is observed. The rate of the reaction is influenced by a change in ionic strength of the medium and the dielectric effect is found to be positive. The latter enables the computation of d_{AB} , the size of the activated complex. Proton inventory studies are made for the reactions in H₂O-D₂O mixtures. Activation parameters are calculated from the Arrhenius plots. The product analyses indicates that the sugars are oxidized to a mixture of aldonic acids, consisting of arabinonic, ribonic, erythronic and glyceric acids. A mechanism consistent with the observed kinetics has been proposed.

Aromatic *N*-halosulfonamides, a group of mild oxidizing agents, have been extensively used for the oxidation of a variety of organic compounds, including aldehydes, amines and amino acids¹. These oxidants contain strongly polarized *N*-linked halogens which are in the +1 state. They undergo two-electron change to form halide ions and the corresponding sulfonamides.

It was reported earlier that the oxidation of sugars with *N*-chlorobenzenesulfonamide and *N*-bromo-*p*-toluenesulfonamide in alkaline solutions involves a sugar-to-oxidant stoichiometry of 1 : 1 for aldoses and 1 : 2 for fructose². And the products were identified as the corresponding aldonic acids for aldose and arabinonic acid for fructose². However, the present study gave a stoichiometry of 3 moles of BAT per mole of sugar. HPLC and GLC-MS analyses of the oxidation products gave different product profiles than that reported earlier².

Results and Discussion

The reactions were carried out with varying concentrations of BAT using constant [OH⁻] and [S] (where S = sugar). The plots of log [BAT] vs time were linear, indicating a first order dependence of reaction rate on [BAT]₀. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) obtained with different [BAT]₀ were similar, confirming the first order dependence of the rate on [BAT]₀. The k_{obs} values increased with increase in [S]₀ (Table 1). The plots of log k_{obs} vs log [S]₀ were linear with unit slopes. The second order rate constant ($k_2 = k_{\text{obs}} / [\text{S}]_0$) were constant within the experimental error (Table 1), demonstrating a first order dependence of the rate on [S]₀. The lines in the plots of k_{obs} vs [S]₀ passed through the origin, indicating that the intermediates formed with the oxi-

Table 1. Effect of varying [S] on the reaction rate at 25° in alkaline medium

[OX] = 0.002 mol dm⁻³, [OH⁻] = 0.02 mol dm⁻³, *I* = 0.3 mol dm⁻³

[Sugar] mol dm ⁻³	D-Glucose		D-Mannose	
	10 ⁴ k_{obs} s ⁻¹	10 ² k_2 dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	10 ⁴ k_{obs} s ⁻¹	10 ² k_2 dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
0.01	1.91	1.91	0.60	0.59
0.02	4.03	2.02	1.24	0.62
0.03	6.03	2.01	1.95	0.64
0.04	7.84	1.96	2.69	0.60
0.05	10.47	2.09	3.47	0.65
0.06	13.00	2.12	4.17	0.63

dant have only transient existence.

At constant [BAT] and [S]₀, the values of k_{obs} increased with an increase in [NaOH] (Table 2). The order of reaction in hydroxide ions was calculated from the slope of plots of

Table 2. Effect of varying [OH⁻] on the reaction rate at 25° in alkaline medium

[OH] = 0.002 mol dm⁻³, [S] = 0.02 mol dm⁻³, *I* = 0.3 mol dm⁻³

[NaOH] mol dm ⁻³	D-Glucose		D-Mannose	
	10 ⁴ k_{obs} s ⁻¹	10 ² k_2 dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	10 ⁴ k_{obs} s ⁻¹	10 ² k_2 dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
0.01	1.00	0.5	0.33	0.2
0.03	8.91	4.5	2.63	1.3
0.04	15.85	7.9	4.79	2.4
0.05	25.12	12.6	7.24	3.6
0.06	35.48	17.7	10.47	5.2

log k_{obs} vs log $[\text{OH}^-]$. These data demonstrated that the reaction follows second order dependence on $[\text{OH}^-]$.

Addition of *p*-toluenesulfonamide to the reaction mixture had no significant effect on the rate. This indicates that the product *p*-toluenesulfonamide was not involved in pre-equilibrium with the oxidant. Addition of NaBr to the reaction mixture had no significant effect on the rates, suggesting that the free bromide ion was not formed before the rate limiting step. Addition of sodium perchlorate increased the rate of reaction. The plots of log k_{obs} vs $I^{1/2}$ (I = ionic strength of medium) were linear with fractional slopes.

The solvent composition of the medium was varied by adding methanol up to 40%. The rate increased with an increase in methanol content. The plots of log k_{obs} vs $1/D$ (D = dielectric constant of medium) were linear with negative slopes. The reaction was studied at different temperatures (298–318 K) and from the Arrhenius plots of log k_{obs} vs $1/T$, the values of activation parameters for the composite reaction were calculated (Table 3). The reactions were performed in deuterium oxide and the solvent-isotope effect, $k_{\text{obs}}(\text{H}_2\text{O}) / k_{\text{obs}}(\text{D}_2\text{O})$, were between 0.5 and 0.6 (Table 4). Proton-inventory studies were made in water-deuterium oxide mixtures.

Table 3. Kinetic and thermodynamic parameters for the oxidation of D-glucose and D-mannose by BAT in alkaline medium

	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	log A
D-Glucose	108.1	105.2	10.2	92.1	15.4
D-Mannose	124.9	121.9	87.7	95.1	17.5

Table 4. Proton inventory studies for the oxidation of sugars by BAT in H₂O-D₂O mixture

$[\text{OX}] = 0.002 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{S}] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{OH}^-] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 25°

Atom fraction of deuterium (n)	D-Glucose	D-Mannose
0.00	4.03	1.24
0.25	4.70	1.41
0.50	5.41	1.65
0.75	6.01	2.01
0.93	6.63	2.26

The identical orders with respect to both BAT and sugars suggest a common mechanism for the oxidation of sugars by BAT. The organic haloamines behave as strong electrolyte in aqueous solutions and several equilibria present are predominantly pH-dependant^{3,4}. Although the oxidizing species in acidic solutions of BAT are RNBrH, RNBr₂ and hypobromous acid, it has been established that in alkaline medium, RNBr⁻ is the active oxidant^{4,5}.

In alkaline solutions, sugars undergo enolization to form enediolate anions⁶. In the absence of other reactants, these anions undergo epimerization and isomerization (Lobry de Bruyn-Alberda van Ekenstein transformation) to form a mixture of isomeric aldoses and ketoses⁶. However, in the presence of BAT, the enediolate anions (E^-) react with RNBr⁻ to form intermediate (X), which in turn undergoes cleavage to form the products (Table 5),

Scheme 1

Table 5. HPLC analysis of the products formed by the oxidation of sugars by BAT in alkaline medium

Sugar	Mole of BAT consumed per mole of sugar	Products (mole%) ^a				
		Arabinonic acid	Ribonic acid	Erythronic and threonic acid ^b	Glyceric acid	Hexonic acid
D-Mannose	2.5	36	19	35	4	6
D-Glucose	2.8	35	21	36	3	5

^aBased on the peak areas normalized using response factors obtained by analyzing standard aldonic acid solutions. The mole proportions of products formed at 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 8 and 16 h were similar to those observed at 24 h, except that the presence of six-carbon aldonic acids was evident only after 4 h. Similar product profile was observed even when the reactions were carried out with 0.01 M sugars and 0.01 M BAT.

^bThe shoulder at the tailing edge of the peak 2 in Fig. 2 represents threonic acid (2–4% of total aldonic acids formed).

In view of the observed first-order dependence of rate on $[\text{BAT}]_0$ and $[\text{S}]_0$ and second-order dependence on $[\text{OH}^-]$, Scheme 1 is proposed for the oxidation of sugars by BAT in alkaline solutions. Assuming steady state condition for E^- , rate law (eqn. 1) can be derived,

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{d[\text{BAT}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{S}] [\text{OH}^-]^2 [\text{BAT}]}{k_{-1} [\text{H}_2\text{O}] + k_2 [\text{OH}^-] [\text{BAT}]} \quad (1)$$

Since there is a second order dependence of rate on $[\text{OH}^-]$, the assumption that $k_{-1} [\text{H}_2\text{O}] > k_2 [\text{OH}^-] [\text{BAT}]$, where k_2 represents the specific reaction rate constant for the rate-limiting step, is valid. Thus, rate law (eqn. 1) is reduced to

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{d[\text{BAT}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{S}] [\text{OH}^-]^2 [\text{BAT}]}{k_{-1} [\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \quad (2)$$

which agrees with observed rate = $k_{\text{obs}} [\text{S}] [\text{OH}^-]^2 [\text{BAT}]$
The formation of pentonic acids and erythronic acid by

the loss of one and two carbon atoms, respectively, and minor proportion of hexonic acid, suggest that these sugars reacts with BAT mainly through keto-enolic anion intermediates. The formation of only minor amount of hexonic acids further suggests that hexoses react extremely slowly with BAT in the aldo-enolic forms. This conclusion agrees with the formation of only minor amount of mannonic acid despite the existence of a significant amount of unreacted mannose in the aldoose form even after 24 h of incubation with

BAT. The resistance of 2-deoxy-D-arabino-hexose and 2-acetamido-2-deoxyglucose (although these hexoses can enolize, they can not isomerize to keto-forms) to oxidation by BAT further supports this prediction. HPLC of the reaction mixture at various time points, demonstrates that the fructose isomer formed by the alkali-catalyzed isomerization is the species that reacts with BAT. Based on these considerations, a plausible mechanism for the oxidation of sugars by BAT is proposed in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

In the proposed mechanism (Scheme 2), the anion (E^-) reacts with BAT to form intermediates X1 and X2. The loss of hydrogen can occur at either C-1 or C-3 to form C-1 – C-2 or C-2 – C-3 enediols containing chloroxyl group at C-2. Since these enediols contain polarized double bonds, hydroxide ion can add at C-2 to form intermediates X1 and X2; the formation of X2 accompanies epimerization at C-2 and C-3. X1 and X2 then can undergo cleavage of C–C bonds between C-1 and C-2, the former giving arabinonic acid and the latter forming a mixture of arabinonic and ribonic acids. The cleavage of C–C bonds between C-2 and C-3 in X1 and X2, yields aldotetrose without epimerization at C-4. The aldotetrose further oxidizes to yield erythronic acid and a minor proportion of threonic acid (Table 4). The reaction can proceed further with the cleavage of C–C bonds to form glyceric acid.

Although in the proposed mechanism, BAT is shown to react with preformed enediol-anion intermediate, it is possible that the ring-opening of sugars is assisted by BAT. Since the furanosidic form of sugars is expected to be less energetic compared with the pyranosidic form, BAT may preferentially react with the furanosidic form rather than pyranosidic form. Consistent with this suggestion, it is known that a significant proportion of fructose exists in the furanose configuration⁷.

Previous studies, using oxidants that are closely related to BAT, reported a sugar to oxidant stoichiometry of 1 : 1². The reported lower stoichiometry was due to the premature (within 6 h after incubation) determination of BAT in the reaction mixture. Furthermore, in previous studies, paper chromatography was used for identification of the oxidation products². Because of poor resolution under the conditions employed, the product identification was not definitive. In the present study, the stoichiometry was estimated after an incubation period of 24 h and the products were rigorously analyzed using HPLC and GLC-MS. Thus the results of the present study suggests a novel pathway (Scheme 2) for the oxidation of sugars by BAT.

The oxidation products of sugars were also analyzed at 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 8, 16 and 24 h. The formation of six-carbon aldonic acids was observed only after 4 h, revealing that the lower-carbon aldonic acids were not derived from the initially formed six-carbon aldonic acids. Consistent with these data, D-gluconic and D-mannonic acids were not oxidized by BAT.

HPLC analysis of reaction mixtures at various time points further indicated that, whereas 15–20% of glucose was isomerized into fructose within 30 min, less than 5% of

mannose was isomerized to fructose at 30 min. Under similar conditions, 10–15% of fructose was isomerized to glucose. Parallel to this observation, a significant amount of mannose (retention time 4.25 min) was not oxidized by BAT, even though under similar conditions, glucose and fructose (retention time 4.25 and 5.0 min, respectively) were almost completely oxidized. Furthermore, although a large proportion of mannose remained in the reaction mixture even after 24 h of incubation at 25°, only a small proportion of mannonic acid was formed (Table 5). Thus, the ease of aldose-ketose tautomerization, the relative rates of oxidation and the product profile suggest that hexoses undergo oxidation by BAT in the keto(fructo)-enolic form but not in the aldo-enolic form. Furthermore, 2-deoxy-D-arabino-hexose and 2-acetamido-2-deoxy-D-glucose were resistant to oxidation by BAT. This is likely due to the inability of these sugars to isomerize to a keto form and the results agree with the conclusion that aldohexoses react with BAT in the keto form.

The following results supports the above conclusion.

(i) For the reaction involving a fast pre-equilibrium H^+ or OH^- ion-transfer, the rate increases in deuterium oxide medium because D_3O^+ is a stronger acid and DO^- is stronger base. Therefore, the observed increase of oxidation rate in deuterium oxide agrees with the fast pre-equilibrium transfer of OH^- ion⁷ (step I in Scheme 1). The dependence of rate constant (k_{obs}^n) on n (n = the atom fraction of deuterium oxide in a solvent mixture of water and deuterium oxide) is given by the Gross-Butler equation^{8,9}.

(ii) A comparison of the plots of k_{obs} vs n with the standard curves¹⁰ suggests a single proton exchange in the transition state. Further, the value of isotopic fraction factors for the isotopically exchangeable hydrogen site in the reaction was calculated from the slope of the plot of k_{obs}^0 / k_{obs}^n vs n . The value was about 0.6, which closely resembles fractionation factor of OH^- ion.

(iii) Addition of methanol to the reaction medium decreased the rates. The plots of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $1/D$ (D = dielectric constant) were linear with negative slopes. Assuming a double sphere model⁸ for the reaction, the value of the size of the activated/complex was calculated from the slope. The derived d_{AB} values for D-glucose and D-mannose are 4.82 and 3.34 Å, respectively. These values are comparable with those obtained for similar reactions¹¹.

(iv) Kinetic investigations with the two hexoses, reveal that there is not much difference in their oxidation behavior and the oxidation follows an identical rate law with BAT in alkaline medium. The positive ΔS^\ddagger shows that there is more

disorder in the transition state while the constancy of ΔG^\ddagger values indicates that a similar mechanism is operative in the oxidation of two hexoses by BAT. And the large ΔG^\ddagger value indicates the high solvated state of the activated complex.

Experimental

Bromamine-T (BAT) was prepared by the reported method¹². An aqueous solution of the compound was prepared, iodometrically standardized and stored in brown bottles. A 2 M aqueous NaClO₄ was used to maintain a high ionic strength (0.5) to 'swamp' the reaction mixture. D-Glucose and D-mannose (Sigma) were used. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Triple-distilled water was used for preparing aqueous solutions. The solvent isotope studies were made with D₂O (99.4%) supplied by Bhabha Atomic Research Center (India).

In all kinetic studies, pseudo-first order conditions were maintained with respect to the BAT concentration. Stock solutions of alkali, BAT, sugars and sodium perchlorate were maintained at 25°. From these stock solutions, a mixture of sugars, alkali and sodium perchlorate were prepared. The reaction was initiated by the addition of BAT and monitored for two half-lives by iodometric determination of unconsumed BAT at various time-periods. First order rate constant (k_{obs}) were calculated from the plots of $\log [\text{BAT}]_0$ vs time and these were within $\pm 5\%$.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The reaction mixtures containing sugar, alkali and BAT were kept for 24 h at 25°. The unconsumed BAT was determined iodometrically. From these data, the amount of the oxidant consumed per mole of sugar was calculated.

The oxidation products were analyzed by Dionex HPLC with pulsed amperometric detection using a carboPac PA1 high-pH anion-exchange column (4 × 250 mm)³. An isocratic elution with 0.2 M NaOH was used. The products were identified by comparison of the HPLC retention times with retention times of the standard aldonic acids and by GLC-MS.

For GLS-MS characterization, the reaction mixture was extracted with diethyl ether to remove *p*-toluenesulfonamide and then passed through AG 50 W-X12 (H⁺) and AG 4-X4 (base) resins. The AG 4-X4 resins were eluted with 1 M

pyridine-1 M acetic acid (pH 5.2) and lyophilized. The products were converted into their trimethylsilyl derivatives and then analyzed by GLC-MS. Product analysis indicated that arabinonic, ribonic, erythronic and glyceric acids are the major oxidation products for both the sugars. In addition, small proportions of hexonic acids were formed. Incubation of sugars with alkali alone, under the reaction conditions, did not degrade the sugars to significant extents.

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